

Career Management and Job Satisfaction among Employees in National Research Institute for Chemical Technology (NARICT), Basawa-Zaria, Nigeria

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Abstract

Employee Career Management and Job Satisfaction are crucial factors that influence organisational performance and productivity. They are factors that are vital in ensuring employee engagement, retention, and optimal productivity in organisations across the globe. This paper explored Career Management and Job Satisfaction Among Employees in National Research Institute for Chemical Technology (NARICT), Basawa-Zaria, Nigeria. It highlights the Role of Career Management and Job Satisfaction of Organisations in Nigeria; exploring Career Management for Job Satisfaction in National Research Institute for Chemical Technology (NARICT); the Impact of Career Management and Job Satisfaction for Retention of Employees in National Research Institute for Chemical Technology (NARICT); Components of Effective Impact of Employees' Career Management and Job Satisfaction in Organisations; Challenges of Employees' Career Management and Job Satisfaction in National Research Institute for Chemical Technology (NARICT) and concludes that, for National Research Institute for Chemical Technology (NARICT), Basawa, Zaria to regain its reputation as reputable research institute and remain competitive, there is the need for the management to recognise and invest in Employees' Career Management Initiatives in fostering job satisfaction, improve employee retention, satisfied workforce, and enhance productivity for the sustainability of the Institute's organisational mandate.

Keywords: Employee, Career Management, Job Satisfaction, NARICT

Introduction

The impact of employee career management and job satisfaction are critical factors that influence the overall productivity and well-being of workers in any organisation. In Nigerian organisations, these elements are essential for ensuring that employees are motivated, productive and committed to their roles. Career management in organisation plays a significant role in shaping the work experience of employees, influencing their productivity and job satisfaction. In Nigeria, the organisations constitute a significant part of the economy, with many employees engaged in government owned institutions, ministries, departments and agencies. Effective career management in such settings is key to fostering employee job satisfaction and retaining talent (Okpara & Wynn, 2007).

Career management in organisations involves systematic processes of developing and supporting employees' professional growth, including recruitment, training, promotion, and membership. In contrast, job satisfaction refers to the degree to which employees are content with their roles, work environments, relationships with supervisors and opportunities for growth (Oluwajomoko & Ojo, 2021). A clear understanding of the relationship between career management and job satisfaction can help policy makers and public sector managers design effective strategies for implementing the experience of employees. In Nigeria, public organisation institutions have been criticised for their lack of structural career management processes. The deficiency can lead to feelings of stagnation among employees and a lack of motivation. Research has consistently shown that career management initiatives play a significant role in enhancing job satisfaction. Employees who see opportunities for growth, development, and promotion are more likely to feel satisfied with their jobs and remain loyal to the organisation (Nwadoani, 2017).

However, the National Research Institute for Chemical Technology (NARICT), Basawa-Zaria, an organisation in Nigeria under the Federal Ministry of Innovation, Science and Technology, plays a significant role as a public sector in fostering research, innovation and technological advancement, which are essential for national development. As a research-focused institution, NARICT depends heavily on a skilled, motivated and satisfied workforce to drive its mission of promoting sustainable chemical technology, and has not fully explored career management and job satisfaction. Therefore, if career management in NARICT when strategically implemented, can lead to higher job satisfaction,

while the reverse also holds true – when employees are satisfied with their jobs, they are more likely to be motivated, productive, and loyal to the organisation.

Role of Career Management and Job Satisfaction of Organisations in Nigeria (CMAJSO)

In the 21st century, organisations globally, including those in Nigeria, have come to recognise that employees are their most valuable assets. The role of career management and job satisfaction in shaping organisational successes has garnered increasing attention in both academic and professional institutions. These two factors are interrelated and significantly impact employees' productivity, retention, motivation and overall organisational performance in diverse ways which include:

Career Management and its Impact on Organisations

Career management refers to the processes by which an organisation helps employees plan and manage their career paths within the organisation. It involves initiatives that promote career growth through training, membership, job retention, performance evaluations, and clear career progression paths. In Nigeria, career management has become a critical tool for enhancing employees' engagement and organisational commitment. A well-structured career management system helps employees align their personal goals with organisational objectives, thereby fostering a culture of loyalty and satisfaction (Akinyemi & Adebayo, 2018).

Studies have shown that career management practices in organisations lead to better employee performance, motivation, and job satisfaction. In Nigeria, organisations where there is a rising focus on talent retention, effective career management can lead to a competitive edge in the labour market. For instance, providing employees with clear career pathways and opportunities for advancement is a key to improving employee engagement and reducing turnover rates (Alabi, 2016).

Job Satisfaction and Organisational Outcomes

Job satisfaction refers to the level of commitment employees feel regarding their work, which can be influenced by various factors such as work environment, compensation, job role clarity, and management style. Job satisfaction plays a crucial role in determining employees' performance, commitment, and retention. In Nigeria, job satisfaction is often tied to the broader socio-economic and organisational environment, where factors such as job security, salary satisfaction, work-life

balance, and interpersonal relationship at the workplace, heavily influence employees' contentment (Mbah & Ikemefuna, 2012). Organisations that prioritise job satisfaction tend to have a more motivated and productive workforce. In the Nigerian context, employees who are satisfied with their jobs are more likely to go above and beyond in their roles, contribute to the organisation's success, and exhibit greater organisational citizenship (Okpara, 2011). Conversely, dissatisfaction can lead to negative outcomes such as absenteeism, reduced performance, and a high turnover rate, which is a concern for many Nigerian organisations

Career management refers to the process through which organisations help employees plan and direct their career growth within the organisation. This process includes career counselling, training and development, promotions, job retention, and monitoring. Career management helps employees gain clarity about their career goals and develop skills that align with the needs of the organisation (DeCenzo & Robbins, 2016). Career management in Nigerian organisations is often linked with opportunities for advancement and access to resources for skill acquisition (Osabiya, 2015). According to research by Adebayo & Owolabi (2018), Nigerian organisations that implement structured career management programmes experience lower turnover rates and higher employee morale, in Nigeria, the practice of career management is still in its nascent stages in many organisations including the National Research Institute for Chemical Technology, which needs to become more competitive by providing the required career management and increasingly recognising the need to invest in their employees' growth and retention for greater research productivity and organisational development.

Exploring Career Management for Job Satisfaction in National Research Institute for Chemical Technology (NARICT)

Ultimately, exploring career management in NARICT would enhance job satisfaction. The relationship between career management and job satisfaction in organisations like NARICT has not been fully explored, particularly in the context of Nigerian institutions. Job satisfaction refers to the level of contentment employees feel about their work, which affects their performance, motivation, and overall well-being. It encompasses several factors, including work environment, compensation, recognition, and career growth opportunities (Locke, 1976). Research has shown consistency that

career management initiatives play a significant role in enhancing job satisfaction, which is hardly found among NARICT employees, whose best practice and competent employees always look for greener pastures or better offers elsewhere instead of being retained with job satisfaction, after which they must achieve some certain qualifications for best practice. Employees who see opportunities for growth, development with their promotion are more likely to feel satisfied with their jobs, and remain loyal to the organisation (Nwadiamo, 2017). In Nigeria where job security can be concerned due to high unemployment rates, career development becomes even more critical in influencing job satisfaction.

According to a study by Akinyemi (2019), stated that Nigerian employees report high levels of job satisfaction when they perceive that their employer is committed to their career advancement. He further stated that, organisations that invest in career management practices contribute to building a supportive work culture. When employees feel that their employer is investing in their long-term career success, it fosters a sense of loyalty and commitment. This sense of job security and progression is quite required in NARICT, because it leads to positive attitudes towards work and organisational goals, ultimately improving employees' performance and satisfaction.

The Impact of Career Management and Job Satisfaction for Retention of Employees in National Research Institute for Chemical Technology

The impact of career management and job satisfaction are strategies that contribute to higher satisfaction and retention by aligning employees' career goals with organisational objectives, fostering a sense of advancement and fulfilment. Career development are opportunities that form the basis that impact employees' career management and job satisfaction, which employees are likely to feel more committed to their roles, resulting in enhanced job satisfaction. Studies have shown that employees who perceive the impact of career management have clear career paths and opportunities for advancement are more likely to have a higher job satisfaction level (Herzberg, 1996). Thus, organisations like NARICT can improve job satisfaction and overall productivity by focusing on the impact of employees' career management and development for job satisfaction and retention.

The impact of employees' career management on job satisfaction extends to employee retention. In Nigeria, higher turnover rates of employment and recruitment have been a significant challenge for many organisations, especially in competitive organisations like NARICT. According to a study by Chinomnso & Olaniran (2020), employees who perceive limited career development opportunities are more likely to leave an organisation in search of better prospects elsewhere. On the other hand, organisations that provide clear career paths, professional programmes, and membership are most able to retain their top talent and best practice, which leads to greater stability and productivity.

In most Nigerian organisations, particularly in NARICT, employees are more likely to stay in the organisation only if NARICT fully explores career management and job satisfaction development strategies that offer competitive opportunities, rewards to best practice, membership, combined with leadership career advancement. Those trends underscore the importance why NARICT needs to integrate career management development strategies into their organisational broader Human Resources Management (HRM) framework. As highlighted by Nwadini (2017), employee retention is a key indicator of job satisfaction, and career management development programmes plays a critical role in this dynamic.

Components of Effective Impact of Employees' Career Management and Job Satisfaction in Organisations

In order for National Research Institute for Chemical Technology (NARICT) to have an effective impact of employees' career management and job satisfaction, which is very essential in shaping the workforce dynamic in any country, Nigeria inclusive, there is the need to explore, understand and build on the following construct components that are interconnected and influence overall organisational performance, retention, productivity, growth and sustainability:

- i. **Increased Job Satisfaction:** Effective career management practices result in higher job satisfaction levels. When employees see clear paths to advance their careers, their engagement. Nigerian organisations that provide opportunities for training, promotions, and personal development enhance employees' overall satisfaction with their roles (Iwu, 2020).

- ii. **Higher Retention Rates:** Organisations that offer robust career management systems see lower turnover rates. In Nigeria, job satisfaction is closely linked to retention as employees are more likely to stay with organisations that support their career growth. This reduces the costs associated with high turnover, such as recruitment and training new staff (Aliyu & Usman, 2019).
- iii. **Improved Employees' Performance:** When employees are satisfied with their career development opportunities and their job satisfaction is high, their performances tend to improve, motivated and well-supported employees contribute more to organisational goals, leading to improved productivity. This is especially important in competitive organisations in Nigeria where performance is key to organisation success (Olatunji, 2021).
- iv. **Organisational commitment:** Career management programmes that provide clear direction for employees can foster greater organisational commitment. In Nigeria, employees who feel their professional goals align with the organisation's objectives are more likely to demonstrate loyalty and a strong work ethic, further enhancing overall organisational success (Ekundayo & Akinbode, 2020).
- v. **Enhanced Employee Well-being:** Job satisfaction contributes to the overall well-being of employees. When employees experience job satisfaction through career management, it affects their mental and emotional health positively. Nigerian organisations that prioritise career management tend to have employees who report lower stress levels and greater work-life satisfaction (Olufunke & Falola, 2019).

The Challenges

Despite the effective impact of career management and job satisfaction, there are several challenges in NARICT that hinder the effectiveness of these practices, which include:

- i. **Inadequate Management Support:** The Institute's Management support is not adequate enough for maximum career management and job satisfaction due to certain bureaucratic

systems that can stifle employees' motivation and career progression. This bureaucratic approach often leads to dissatisfaction as employees perceive limited chances for promotion and career growth (Oludaya *et al.*, 2019).

- ii. **Lack of Structured Career Development Programme:** NARICT does not have adequate well-structured career development programmes. This has affected career management for job satisfaction in the Institute due to lack of resources and the commitment to develop and implement comprehensive career development plans. This lack of structure can lead to employees feeling undervalued or stagnant in their roles. According to Akinyemi *et al.* (2020), the absence of clear career paths often results in high employee turnover and reduced job satisfaction. The limited career growth opportunities can negatively affect morale and organisational loyalty.
- iii. **Political and Favouritism Issues:** The issues of political and favouritism has brought a lot of inconsistency in most of the Institute projects, which has caused several setbacks in research outcome. These issues can undermine employee morale, leading to dissatisfaction. Promotion of career opportunities may not always be based on merit, but on personal relationship or favouritism. This causes frustration among employees who feel their efforts and talents are not being recognised. According to Nwogugu (2019), political factors within the workplace undermine trust in the organisation, affecting employee satisfaction and retention.
- iv. **Lack of Work-Life Balance:** Work-life balance in NARICT has been one of the major challenges affecting employee career management and job satisfaction in which employees take advantage of the opportunity and come to work at their convenience and not according to organisational regulation. The inability to balance work and personal life can lead to turnout and a decline in job satisfaction. Nigerian workers in both the public and private sector often report high levels of stress due to the demanding nature of their job, further diminishing their job satisfaction and career development opportunities (Oluwaseun & Yemi, 2021).

- v. **Inadequate Training and Development Programmes:** The issues of inadequate professional training and development programme has created a lot of setbacks of employees career management and job satisfaction. In most cases, there is no plan induction training for newly employed staff in the organisation, which has affected staff attitude to work. Without sufficient training and development programmes, employees may not possess the skills necessary to perform their responsibilities and advance in their careers, leading to frustration and dissatisfaction. Training and development programmes are key factors that contribute to both career progression and satisfaction. However, these programmes are often either poorly executed or non-existent, particularly in most organisations (Afolabi, 2017).

Conclusion

Career management plays a pivotal role in influencing job satisfaction in most organisations. Employees who perceive opportunities for career advancement and personal development are more likely to be satisfied with jobs and remain with their employers. As the Nigerian labour market continues to evolve, organisations that invest in robust career management improve employees' morale, reduce turnover rates and enhance organisation performance. For National Research Institute for Chemical Technology (NARICT), Basawa, Zaria to regain its reputation as reputable research institute and remain competitive, there is the need for the management to recognise and invest in employee's career management initiatives in fostering job satisfaction, improve employee retention, satisfied workforce, and enhance productivity for the sustainability of the Institute organisational mandate.

Recommendations

- i. **Adequate Management Support:** The management of the Institute needs to provide adequate support to enhance employees career management and job satisfaction to enable employees to put in their best in carrying out their responsibilities for better performance and productivity.

- ii. **Provision of Well Structured Career Development Programme:** There is the need for the management of the Institute to establish a well-structured career development programme and also provide the required financial support for the development of employees on specialised areas of the Institute's activities for the development of the Institute's mandate.
- iii. **Political and Favouritism Issues:** The management of the Institute needs to avoid political and favouritism and give equal rights to all employees and use loyal and committed employees when there are needs of delegation to encourage others to put in their best in performing their responsibilities.
- iv. **Adequate Work-Life Balance:** There is the need to provide work-life balance opportunities to enable employees to be free motivated by coming to work regularly and also build on their attitude to work by observing normal organisational regulations and reporting to duty on time and also closing at the required time as stipulated by work schedule. They will help in improving employees' performance and productivity in the Institute.
- v. **Adequate Training and Development Programme:** There is a need for the management to establish adequate professional training and development programmes that will equip employees with ideas and skills that will boost their job performance and develop professionalism in their area of duty for effective productivity. Basically, training is a key factor that contributes to employees career management and job satisfaction.

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